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Abstract

Let $S(h, k)$ be the least positive integer such that any 2-coloring of the interval $[1, S(h, k)]$ must admit either

- (i) a monochromatic solution to $x_1 + \dots + x_{h-1} = x_h$ with $x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_h$ or
- (ii) a monochromatic solution to $x_1 + \dots + x_{k-1} = x_k$ with $x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_k$.

We prove $S(3, 3) = 9$, $S(3, 4) = 16$, and for all $k \geq 5$,

$$S(3, k) = \begin{cases} 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 3 & \text{if } k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}, \\ 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 4 & \text{if } k \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

1. Introduction

Let \mathbb{N} denote the set of positive integers and $[a, b] = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : a \leq n \leq b\}$. A mapping $\chi : [a, b] \rightarrow [1, t]$ is called a t -coloring of $[a, b]$. Let L_m denote the system of inequalities given by

$$x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_{m-1} = x_m, \quad x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_m.$$

A solution n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m to L_m is *monochromatic* if $\chi(n_i) = \chi(n_j)$ for $1 \leq i, j \leq m$. Henceforth, we assume a *two-coloring* ($t = 2$) of the interval and denote each color by *red* and *blue*. Furthermore, a monochromatic solution to L_m such that $\chi(n_1) = \chi(n_2) = \dots = \chi(n_m) = \textit{red}$ will be called a “*red solution*,” and likewise for a “*blue solution*.” Lastly, we define $S(h, k)$ to be the least positive integer such that every coloring of the interval $[1, S(h, k)]$ by the colors *red* and *blue* contains either a *red solution* to L_k or a *blue solution* to L_h .

In the following proofs, we show that $S(3, 3) = 9$, $S(3, 4) = 16$, and for all $k \geq 5$,

$$S(3, k) = \begin{cases} 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 3 & \text{if } k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}, \\ 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 4 & \text{if } k \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

2. The Lower Bound

Lemma 1. (Lower Bound) *For $k \geq 3$,*

$$S(3, k) \geq N = \begin{cases} 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 3 & \text{if } k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}, \\ 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 4 & \text{if } k \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Consider a coloring of $\chi : [1, N - 1] \rightarrow \{\textit{blue}, \textit{red}\}$ defined as follows. For $n \in [1, N - 1]$, let

$$\chi(n) = \begin{cases} \textit{blue} & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ and } n \leq k(k - 1)/2, \\ \textit{blue} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ and } n \geq k(k - 1), \\ \textit{red} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We claim this coloring has no *blue solution* to L_3 and no *red solution* to L_k .

Suppose $n_1 + n_2 = n_3$, where $n_1 < n_2 < n_3$, is a *blue solution* to L_3 on the interval $[1, N - 1]$. Suppose $n_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Then $n_1 < n_2 \leq k(k - 1)/2$, which implies $n_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and $n_3 < k(k - 1)$. Since $n_3 = n_1 + n_2 \equiv (1 + 1) \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, we must have that $n_3 \geq k(k - 1)$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, $n_2 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$.

Hence, $n_3 > n_2 \geq k(k - 1)$, which implies $n_3 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, which then implies $n_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Therefore, $n_2 > n_1 \geq k(k - 1)$, which implies $n_3 = n_1 + n_2 \geq k(k - 1) + (k(k - 1) + 2) > N - 1$, another contradiction implying no such *blue solution* to L_3 exists.

Next, suppose $n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_{k-1} = n_k$, where $n_1 < n_2 < \dots < n_k$, is a *red solution* to L_k on the interval $[1, N - 1]$. Let q denote the minimal sum of $k - 2$ *red numbers*. Clearly, $q = \sum_{i=1}^{k-2} 2i = k^2 - 3k + 2$.

If $n_{k-1} \leq k(k - 1)/2$, then $n_i \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ for $i \in [1, k - 1]$. This implies $n_k \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, which implies $n_k < k(k - 1)$, but this is a contradiction since $k(k - 1) > n_k \geq q + 2(k - 1) = k(k - 1)$. Therefore, $n_{k-1} > k(k - 1)/2$.

If $k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}$, then $n_k > q + k(k - 1)/2 = 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 2 = N - 1$, a contradiction that implies $k \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$.

If $n_{k-1} = k(k - 1)/2 + 1$, then $n_i \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ for all $i \in [1, k - 1]$, which implies $n_k \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Since n_k is red, $n_k < k(k - 1)$, which is a contradiction since $n_k \geq q + k(k - 1)/2 + 1$. Therefore, $n_{k-1} > k(k - 1)/2 + 1$, which implies $n_k \geq q + k(k - 1)/2 + 2 = 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 4 = N$. \square

3. The Upper Bound

Throughout this section, let p denote the sum of the first k red numbers and let r_i and b_i denote the i^{th} red and blue numbers, respectively. Then, $r_i < r_j$ and $b_i < b_j$, for all $i < j$.

Lemma 2. *For $n \geq 3$, if at least $n + 1$ numbers in the interval $[1, 2n]$ are colored blue, then the only coloring that avoids a blue solution to L_3 is given by*

$$\chi(x) = \begin{cases} \text{red} & \text{if } x \in [1, n - 1], \\ \text{blue} & \text{if } x \in [n, 2n]. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Since the case $n = 3$ is trivial, assume $n > 3$.

Case 1. $\chi(2n) = \text{red}$. We proceed via induction on n . For some $n > 3$, assume the claim holds for $n - 1$. To avoid a blue solution on the interval $[1, 2(n - 1)]$, we must have $\chi(x) = \text{blue}$ for all $x \in [(n - 1), 2(n - 1)]$ and $\chi(x) = \text{red}$ for all $x \in [1, n - 2]$. Since we need another blue in the interval $[1, 2n]$, the number $(2n - 1)$ must be blue, but then $(n - 1) + n = (2n - 1)$ is a blue solution to L_3 .

Case 2. $\chi(2n) = \text{blue}$. By the pigeonhole principle, $\chi(n) = \text{blue}$, since otherwise one of the pairs $\{x, 2n - x\}$ with $1 \leq x < n$ would be all blue giving us the blue solution $(x) + (2n - x) = 2n$. Now suppose $\chi(1) = \text{blue}$, which implies the pair $\{n - 1, n + 1\}$ is all red. Hence, some other pair $\{x, 2n - x\}$ with $1 \leq x < n - 1$, is all blue and we get a contradiction. Therefore, $\chi(1) = \text{red}$; hence $\chi(2n - 1) = \text{blue}$, otherwise some other pair $\{x, 2n - x\}$ with $2 \leq x \leq n - 2$ would be all blue, giving us a contradiction as before. But then we must have $\chi(n - 1) = \text{red}$ since $(n - 1) + n = (2n - 1)$; hence $\chi(n + 1) = \text{blue}$. But then we must have $\chi(n - 2) = \text{red}$ since $(n - 2) + (n + 1) = (2n - 1)$; hence $\chi(n + 2) = \text{blue}$. Continuing in this manner, we get the desired coloring. \square

Corollary 1. *To avoid a blue solution to L_3 , $r_i \leq 2i + 1$ for all i .*

Proof. The claim is easily proven for r_1 and r_2 . Suppose $r_i > 2i + 1$ for some $i \geq 3$. This would imply at least $i + 1$ numbers are colored blue in the interval $[1, 2i]$. Applying Lemma 2 gives us that $\chi(i) = \chi(i + 1) = \text{blue}$. Since there are $2i + 1 - (i - 1) = i + 2$ blue integers in $[1, 2i + 1]$, $\chi(2i + 1) = \text{blue}$ as well, but this yields the blue solution $i + (i + 1) = 2i + 1$. \square

Corollary 2. *There exists at least k integers in the interval $[1, N]$ colored red, that is, p exists.*

Proof. If p does not exist, then by Corollary 1, $r_{k-1} \leq 2k - 1$, which implies that all numbers in $[2k, N]$ are colored *blue*, while the Pigeonhole Principle ensures that some number in $[1, k]$ is also colored *blue*, say $x \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$. But then $x + 2k = x + 2k \leq N$ is a *blue* solution for $k \geq 4$, a contradiction. The case $k = 3$ can be done separately by hand varying this argument and handling several cases. \square

Corollary 3. *Let $i > b_1$ and $i \geq 3$. To avoid a blue solution to L_3 , $r_i \leq 2i$.*

Proof. Suppose $r_i > 2i$. Then Corollary 1 implies $r_i = 2i + 1$. Therefore, the interval $[1, 2i + 1]$ must contain exactly $i + 1$ *blue* numbers. Since $i \geq 3$, Lemma 2 implies that the interval $[1, i - 1]$ is all *red*, but this contradicts the hypothesis $b_1 < i$. \square

Lemma 3. (P Lemma) *The following hold:*

- (i) *If $b_1 = 1$, then $p \leq k^2 + k - 12 + r_1 + r_2 + r_3$,*
- (ii) *If $1 < b_1 \leq k$, then $p \leq k^2 + k + 1 - b_1(b_1 - 1)/2$,*
- (iii) *If $b_1 > k$, then $p = k(k + 1)/2$.*

Proof. (i) If $b_1 = 1$, then by Corollary 3

$$\begin{aligned} p = r_1 + r_2 + r_3 + \sum_{i=4}^k r_i &\leq r_1 + r_2 + r_3 + \sum_{i=4}^k 2i \\ &= k^2 + k - 12 + r_1 + r_2 + r_3. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) If $1 < b_1 \leq k$, then by Corollaries 1 and 3

$$\begin{aligned} p = \sum_{i=1}^{b_1-1} r_i + r_{b_1} + \sum_{i=b_1+1}^k r_i &\leq \sum_{i=1}^{b_1-1} i + (2b_1 + 1) + \sum_{i=b_1+1}^k r_i \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^{b_1-1} i + (2b_1 + 1) + \sum_{i=b_1+1}^k 2i \\ &= k^2 + k + 1 - b_1(b_1 - 1)/2. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) If $b_1 > k$, then $p = \sum_{i=1}^k r_i = \sum_{i=1}^k i = k(k + 1)/2$. \square

Given a valid colouring, the upper bound for p can be improved by modifying Lemma 3. For example, for $k \geq 6$, if $r_1 = 1, b_1 = 2, r_2 = 3$, and $r_3 = 4$, then

$$p \leq k^2 + k + 1 - b_1(b_1 - 1)/2 - (5 - r_2) - (6 - r_3) = k^2 + k - 4.$$

Fact 1. *If $k \geq 6$, then $k^2 + k - 5 \leq N$.*

Corollary 4. *If $p - r_j \leq N$ for some $j \in [1, k]$, then to avoid a red solution to L_k , $\chi(p - r_i) = \text{blue}$ for all $i \in [j, k]$.*

Proof. If $\chi(p - r_i) = \text{red}$ for some $i \in [j, k]$, then we get the red solution to L_k

$$r_1 + r_2 + \dots + r_{i-1} + r_{i+1} + r_{i+2} + \dots + r_k = p - r_i,$$

where $p - r_i \leq p - r_j \leq N$ (by hypothesis). Hence, $\chi(p - r_i) = \text{blue}$ for all $i \in [j, k]$. □

Corollary 5. *If $k \geq 6$ and $b_1 > 1$, then $p - r_i \leq N$ for all r_i .*

Proof. We have $p - r_i \leq p - 1$. In view of Fact 1, if $p \leq k^2 + k - 4$, then $p - r_i \leq N$ for all r_i . If $b_1 = 2$, then modifying Lemma 3, we get the following cases:

#	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	n s.t. $p \leq n$
1.	r_1	b_1	b_2	b_3	r_2	r_3	r_4	b_4	b_5	r_5	r_6	r_7	$k^2 + k - 4$
2.	r_1	b_1	b_2	b_3	r_2	r_3	r_4	b_4	r_5	r_6			$k^2 + k - 4$
3.	r_1	b_1	b_2	b_3	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	b_4	b_5	r_6		$k^2 + k - 4$
4.	r_1	b_1	b_2	b_3	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	b_4	r_6			$k^2 + k - 5$
5.	r_1	b_1	b_2	b_3	r_2	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6				$k^2 + k - 6$
6.	r_1	b_1	b_2	r_2	r_3	b_3	b_4	r_4	r_5	r_6			$k^2 + k - 5$
7.	r_1	b_1	b_2	r_2	r_3	b_3	r_4	r_5					$k^2 + k - 5$
8.	r_1	b_1	b_2	r_2	r_3	r_4							$k^2 + k - 4$
9.	r_1	b_1	r_2	b_2	b_3	r_3	r_4	b_4	r_5				$k^2 + k - 4$
10.	r_1	b_1	r_2	b_2	b_3	r_3	r_4	r_5					$k^2 + k - 5$
11.	r_1	b_1	r_2	b_2	r_3	r_4							$k^2 + k - 5$
12.	r_1	b_1	r_2	r_3									$k^2 + k - 4$

Similarly, if $b_1 = 3$ then modifying Lemma 3, we get the following cases:

#	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	n s.t. $p \leq n$
1.	r_1	r_2	b_1	b_2	b_3	b_4	r_3	r_4	r_5	r_6	$k^2 + k - 5$
2.	r_1	r_2	b_1	b_2	b_3	r_3	r_4				$k^2 + k - 4$
3.	r_1	r_2	b_1	b_2	r_3						$k^2 + k - 4$
4.	r_1	r_2	b_1	r_3							$k^2 + k - 5$

For $4 \leq b_1 \leq k$, by Lemma 3 we have $p \leq k^2 + k - 5$. For $b_1 > k, p = k(k + 1)/2$ by part (iii) of Lemma 3. For $k \geq 6$ and $b_1 > 1$, we have $p \leq k^2 + k - 4$, and hence,

using Fact 1

$$p - r_i \leq p - 1 \leq (k^2 + k - 4) - 1 = k^2 + k - 5 \leq N$$

for all r_i with $i \in [1, k]$. □

Remark 1. Combining Corollaries 4 and 5, we see that, for $k \geq 6$ and $b_1 > 1$, $\chi(p - r_j) = \text{blue}$ for all $j \in [1, k]$.

Lemma 4. (Upper Bound) For $k \geq 6$,

$$S(3, k) \leq N = \begin{cases} 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 3 & \text{if } k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}, \\ 3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 4 & \text{if } k \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Suppose to the contrary that N is not an upper bound for $k \geq 6$. This occurs if and only if there exists a coloring of $[1, N]$ without a *blue* solution to L_3 and a *red* solution to L_k . Consider the following two cases:

- (1) $\chi(1) = \text{blue}$ (with $k \geq 6$). Suppose $\chi(2) = \text{blue}$. Then $r_1 = 3$ and $r_2 \leq 5$ (by Corollary 1) to avoid *blue* solutions $1 + 2 = 3$ and $1 + 4 = 5$, respectively. Therefore, by Lemma 3 and Corollary 3, we have

$$p \leq k^2 + k - 4 + r_3 \leq k^2 + k + 2,$$

which implies (by Fact 1) that $p - r_i \leq k^2 + k - 5 \leq N$ for $r_i \geq 7$.

If $\chi(x) = \text{blue}$ for some $x \in [6, 7]$, then this implies $\chi(x+1) = \chi(x+2) = \text{red}$ to avoid the *blue* solutions $1 + x = x + 1$ and $2 + x = x + 2$. Corollary 4 implies $\chi(p - x - 1) = \chi(p - x - 2) = \text{blue}$, and then $1 + (p - x - 2) = p - x - 1$ is a *blue* solution since $p - x - 2 \geq k(k + 1)/2 - 9 \geq 12 > 1$. Therefore, $\chi(6) = \chi(7) = \text{red}$. Considering the present information, it can be shown that $p - r_i \leq N$ for $r_i \geq 6$. If $r_2 = 4$, then $p \leq k^2 + k + 1$, otherwise 7 being *red* means that the estimate for r_4 can be improved by one. Now, Corollary 4 gives $\chi(p - 6) = \chi(p - 7) = \text{blue}$. Thus $1 + (p - 7) = p - 6$ is a *blue* solution in view of $p - 8 \geq k(k + 1)/2 - 8 \geq 13 > 1$. So we conclude that $\chi(2) = \text{red}$.

If $b_2 \geq 5$, then $r_2 = 3$, $r_3 = 4$, and, by Lemma 3 and Fact 1,

$$p - r_1 \leq k^2 + k - 12 + r_2 + r_3 = k^2 + k - 5 \leq N,$$

which leads to a contradiction since Corollary 4 gives us the *blue* solution $1 + (p - 4) = p - 3$.

If $b_2 = 4$, then $r_2 = 3$ and $r_3 = 5$, and by Lemma 3 and Fact 1

$$p - r_2 \leq k^2 + k - 12 + r_1 + r_3 = k^2 + k - 5 \leq N.$$

By Corollary 4, $\chi(p - 3) = \chi(p - 5) = \text{blue}$. To avoid a *blue* solution $1 + (p - 6) = p - 5$, we need $\chi(p - 6) = \text{red}$, but by Corollary 4, this implies $\chi(6) = \text{blue}$.

In that case, to avoid the *blue* solution $1 + 6 = 7$, we need $\chi(7) = \textit{red}$, but that yields the *blue* solution $4 + (p - 7) = p - 3$.

Now, suppose $b_3 > r_3$. If $b_2 = 3$, then $r_2 = 4$, $r_3 = 5$ (since $b_3 > r_3$), and by Lemma 3 and Fact 1, $p - r_2 \leq k^2 + k - 5 \leq N$, but that yields the *blue* solution $1 + (p - 5) = p - 4$ (by Corollary 4).

Therefore, $b_3 < r_3$, which implies the interval $[3, 5]$ has two *blue* numbers. Since these *blue* numbers cannot be adjacent, the only valid coloring is $\chi(3) = \chi(5) = \textit{blue}$ and $\chi(4) = \chi(6) = \textit{red}$. With this coloring, Corollary 1, Lemma 3, Corollary 4, and Fact 1 imply that $\chi(p - r_i) = \textit{blue}$, for $i \in [3, k]$.

To avoid the *blue* solution $1 + (p - r_{i+1}) = p - r_i$, we must have $r_{i+1} > r_i + 1$, that is, $\chi(r_i + 1) = \textit{blue}$, for all $i \in [3, k - 1]$. Thus $\chi(7) = \textit{blue}$. Also, to avoid the *blue* solution $1 + b_i = b_{i+1}$, we must have $\chi(b_i + 1) = \textit{red}$, for all $i > 1$. Thus $\chi(8) = \textit{red}$, which implies $\chi(9) = \textit{blue}$, which implies $\chi(10) = \textit{red}$, and continuing in this manner, we get that, for all $x \in [1, 2k]$,

$$\chi(x) = \begin{cases} \textit{red} & \text{if } x \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ \textit{blue} & \text{if } x \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, for all $x \in [1, 2k - 3]$ with $\chi(x) = \textit{blue}$, we must have $\chi(x + (2k - 1)) = \textit{red}$, otherwise we get the *blue* solution $x + (2k - 1) = x + 2k - 1$. This implies $\chi(y) = \textit{red}$ for all $y \in [2k, 4k - 4]$ with $y \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$.

Using the block of even *red* numbers, we can extend the *blue* interval. Clearly, the sum of any $k - 1$ *red* numbers which is less than N must be *blue*. The maximal sum of $k - 1$ *red* numbers from the block is $\sum_{i=0}^{k-2} ((4k - 4) - 2i) = 3k^2 - 5k + 2$, which is clearly greater than N . Furthermore, the minimal sum of $k - 1$ *red* numbers from the block is $\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} 2i = k^2 - k$. Since we can always replace a *red* number in the minimal sum by an adjacent even number which is also *red*, and the maximal sum is greater than N , we get that all even numbers greater than or equal to $k^2 - k$ must be *blue*. This yields the extended coloring

$$\chi(x) = \begin{cases} \textit{red} & \text{if } x \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ and } x \in [2, 4k - 4], \\ \textit{blue} & \text{if } x \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ and } x \in [1, 2k - 1], \\ \textit{blue} & \text{if } x \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ and } x \in [k^2 - k, N]. \end{cases}$$

It can easily be shown that $N \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, implying $\chi(N - 1) = \textit{blue}$. Since $\chi(1) = \chi(3) = \textit{blue}$, we must have $\chi(N) = \chi(N - 2) = \chi(N - 4) = \textit{red}$. Let q be the sum of first $k - 2$ *red* numbers. Then $q = k^2 - 3k + 2$. To avoid a *red* solution to L_k , we must have

$$\chi(N - q) = \chi(N - 2 - q) = \chi(N - 4 - q) = \textit{blue},$$

since $N - 4 - q > r_{k-2} = 2(k - 2)$.

If $k \equiv 0, 1 \pmod{4}$, then we get the *blue* solution

$$(N - q) + (N - 2 - q) = 2(3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 3) - 2(k^2 - 3k + 2) - 2 = k^2 - k.$$

Likewise, if $k \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$, then we get the *blue* solution

$$(N - q) + (N - 4 - q) = 2(3k^2/2 - 7k/2 + 4) - 2(k^2 - 3k + 2) - 4 = k^2 - k.$$

Therefore, $\chi(1) \neq \text{blue}$.

- (2) $\chi(1) = \text{red}$ (with $k \geq 6$). Since $k \geq 6$ and $b_1 > 1$, by Remark 1, we have $\chi(p - r_i) = \text{blue}$ for all $i \in [1, k]$. Let a be the minimum *red* number such that $\chi(a - 1) = \text{blue}$. It can be shown that a exists. Suppose a does not exist, that is, x (say) *red* numbers are followed by $N - x$ *blue* numbers. If $x \geq k(k - 1)/2$, then we have a *red* solution $1 + 2 + \dots + (k - 1) = k(k - 1)/2$, or else we have a *blue* solution $k(k - 1)/2 + (k(k - 1)/2 + 1) = k^2 - k + 1 \leq N$.

If $a < r_k$, then $\chi(p - a) = \text{blue}$, which gives us a potential *blue* solution $(a - 1) + (p - a) = p - 1$. In order for it to be a valid solution, we must have that $a - 1 \neq p - a$. However, since $a = r_i$ for some $i \in [1, k]$, this has already been proven in Corollary 4 ($p - r_i > r_k$ for all $i \in [1, k]$).

The argument of the previous paragraph yields a contradiction unless $p - r_k = p - a = a - 1$, in which case $k + (k + 1) = 2k + 1 \leq \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} i = p - r_k = p - a = a - 1$, from which it is clear in view of the definition of a that $k + (k + 1) = 2k + 1$ is a *blue* solution.

Suppose $b_1 \leq 3k/2$. To avoid the *blue* solution, $b_1 + (b_1 + 1) = 2b_1 + 1$, either $b_1 + 1$ or $2b_1 + 1$ must be *red*, which implies $a \leq 2b_1 + 1 \leq 3k + 1$. Now consider,

$$\begin{aligned} (p - r_k) - 1 + a &= \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} i + (a - 1) = k(k - 1)/2 + (a - 1) \\ &\leq k(k - 1)/2 + (3k + 1) - 1 = (k^2 + 5k)/2 \leq N. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\chi(a) = \text{red}$, to avoid the *red* solution $a + \sum_{i=2}^{k-1} i = (p - r_k) - 1 + a$, we have $\chi(p - r_k + a - 1) = \text{blue}$, which yields the potential *blue* solution

$$(p - r_k) + (a - 1) = (p - r_k) - 1 + a.$$

To be a valid solution, we must have $a - 1 \neq p - r_k$. If $a - 1 = p - r_k$, then $p - r_k + 1 = a$, which implies $\chi(p - r_k + 1) = \text{red}$. However, this is a contradiction since $\chi(p - r_{k-1}) = \text{blue}$ and $r_{k-1} = r_k - 1$.

Therefore, $b_1 > 3k/2$, which implies $\chi(x) = \text{red}$ for all $x \in [1, 3k/2]$. Using this *red* interval, we can create another *blue* interval. The minimum sum of

$k - 1$ red numbers in this interval is $k(k - 1)/2$. If k is even, then the maximal sum is $k^2 - 1$, and if k is odd, then since only integers are colored, we only know that the interval $[1, (3k - 1)/2]$ is colored all red, in which case, the maximal sum of $k - 1$ red integers is $k^2 - k/2 - 1/2$.

Since every integer in this new interval can be represented by a sum of $k - 1$ red numbers, the interval $[k(k - 1)/2, k^2 - k/2 - 1/2]$ must be colored blue to avoid a red solution. Since $k^2 - k + 1$ is in the blue interval, we have the blue solution $k(k - 1)/2 + (k(k - 1)/2 + 1) = k^2 - k + 1$.

Hence, for $k \geq 6$, every coloring of $[1, N]$ has a blue solution to L_3 or a red solution to L_k . □

4. The Cases $3 \leq k \leq 5$

In this section, we formally prove the exact values of $S(3, 3)$ and $S(3, 4)$, and provide the computer proof for the exact value of $S(3, 5)$.

Lemma 5. $S(3, 3) = 9$.

Proof. Let $\chi(1) = \chi(2) = \chi(4) = \chi(8) = \text{red}$ and $\chi(3) = \chi(5) = \chi(6) = \chi(7) = \text{blue}$. This coloring has no red or blue solution to L_3 . Therefore, $S(3, 3) > 8$.

Suppose to the contrary that $S(3, 3) > 9$. Without loss of generality, let blue be the color used 5 or more times from 1 to 9. If $\chi(9) = \text{red}$, then Lemma 2 gives us the red solution $1 + 2 = 3$. Therefore, $\chi(9) = \text{blue}$. We are left with two cases.

Case 1. $\chi(8) = \text{blue}$. To avoid the blue solution $1 + 8 = 9$, we have $\chi(1) = \text{red}$. If $\chi(5) = \text{blue}$, then we must have $\chi(3) = \text{red}$ (to avoid the blue solution $3 + 5 = 8$) and $\chi(4) = \text{red}$ (to avoid the blue solution $4 + 5 = 9$). But then we have the red solution $1 + 3 = 4$. Therefore, $\chi(5) = \text{red}$. To avoid the red solutions $1 + 4 = 5$ and $1 + 5 = 6$, we must have $\chi(4) = \chi(6) = \text{blue}$. Then $\chi(2) = \text{red}$ (to avoid the blue solution $2 + 4 = 6$), which implies $\chi(3) = \text{blue}$ (to avoid the red solution $1 + 2 = 3$), which gives the blue solution $3 + 6 = 9$.

Case 2. $\chi(8) = \text{red}$. If $\chi(7) = \text{red}$, then Lemma 2 gives us the red solution $1 + 7 = 8$. Therefore, $\chi(7) = \text{blue}$, which leads to a contradiction after a chain of implications:

- $\chi(2) = \text{red}$ (to avoid the blue solution $2 + 7 = 9$),
 - $\chi(6) = \text{blue}$ (to avoid the red solution $2 + 6 = 8$),
 - $\chi(1) = \text{red}$ (to avoid the blue solution $1 + 6 = 7$),
 - $\chi(3) = \text{blue}$ (to avoid the red solution $1 + 2 = 3$),
- and hence the blue solution $3 + 6 = 9$. □

Lemma 6. $S(3, 4) = 16$.

Proof. For all $x \in [1, 15]$, let $x \in [6, 12]$ be *blue* and x be *red* otherwise. This coloring has no *blue* solution to L_3 and no *red* solution to L_4 . Therefore, $S(3, 4) > 15$.

Suppose to the contrary that $S(3, 4) > 16$. Then suppose $\chi(1) = \textit{blue}$. Corollary 3 implies $r_i \leq 2i$, for all $i \geq 3$.

Since $r_1 + r_2 + r_4 \leq 3 + 5 + 8 = 16$, we have $\chi(r_1 + r_2 + r_3) = \chi(r_1 + r_2 + r_4) = \textit{blue}$. If $r_4 > r_3 + 2$, we get the *blue* solution $1 + (r_3 + 1) = r_3 + 2$, and if $r_4 = r_3 + 1$, we get the *blue* solution $1 + (r_1 + r_2 + r_3) = r_1 + r_2 + r_4$. Hence, $r_4 = r_3 + 2$. To avoid the *blue* solution $2 + (r_1 + r_2 + r_3) = r_1 + r_2 + r_4$, we must have $\chi(2) = \textit{red}$, that is, $r_1 = 2$, which implies $r_1 + r_3 + r_4 \leq 2 + 6 + 8 = 16$. Thus $\chi(r_1 + r_3 + r_4) = \textit{blue}$.

Applying the same reasoning to r_3 as we did to r_4 , we get that $r_3 = r_2 + 2$. Then to avoid the *blue* solution $4 + (r_1 + r_2 + r_3) = r_1 + r_3 + r_4$, we must have $\chi(4) = \textit{red}$. If $\chi(3) = \textit{red}$, then $r_2 = 3$, and so $r_3 = 4$. But $r_3 \neq r_2 + 1$. Therefore, $\chi(3) = \textit{blue}$, which implies $r_2 = 4$, and so $r_3 = 6$ and $r_4 = 8$. Then we must have $\chi(5) = \chi(7) = \chi(12) = \textit{blue}$, but then we get the *blue* solution $5 + 7 = 12$. Therefore, $\chi(1) = \textit{red}$.

Corollary 1 gives us that $r_2 = 2, 3, 4$, or 5 . We handle these four cases separately.

Case 1. $r_2 = 5$. This implies $\chi(2) = \chi(3) = \chi(4) = \textit{blue}$. Therefore, $\chi(6) = \textit{red}$ and $\chi(7) = \textit{red}$ to avoid the *blue* solutions $2 + 4 = 6$ and $3 + 4 = 7$, respectively. Hence, $\chi(12) = \textit{blue}$ and $\chi(14) = \textit{blue}$ to avoid the *red* solutions $1 + 5 + 6 = 12$ and $1 + 6 + 7 = 14$, respectively. But, then we get the *blue* solution $2 + 12 = 14$.

Case 2. $r_2 = 4$. This implies $\chi(2) = \chi(3) = \textit{blue}$. Therefore, $\chi(5) = \textit{red}$ (to avoid the *blue* solution $2 + 3 = 5$), which implies $\chi(10) = \textit{blue}$ (to avoid the *red* solution $1 + 4 + 5 = 10$). Therefore, $\chi(7) = \textit{red}$ and $\chi(12) = \textit{red}$ to avoid the *blue* solutions $3 + 7 = 10$ and $2 + 10 = 12$, respectively. But then we get the *red* solution $1 + 4 + 7 = 12$.

Case 3. $r_2 = 3$. This implies $\chi(2) = \textit{blue}$. If $r_4 = 9$, then Lemma 2 implies $\chi(2) = \textit{red}$. Thus $r_4 \leq 8$.

If $r_3 \geq 6$, then $\chi(4) = \chi(5) = \textit{blue}$, which implies $r_3 = 6$ (to avoid the *blue* solution $2 + 4 = 6$). Therefore, $\chi(7) = \textit{red}$ (to avoid the *blue* solution $2 + 5 = 7$), which implies $\chi(14) = \textit{blue}$ (to avoid the *red* solution $1 + 6 + 7 = 14$) and $\chi(16) = \textit{blue}$ (to avoid the *red* solution $3 + 6 + 7 = 16$). But then we get the *blue* solution $2 + 14 = 16$. Therefore, $r_3 \leq 5$.

This implies $3 + r_3 + r_4 \leq 16$, which gives us that $\chi(1 + r_3 + r_4) = \chi(3 + r_3 + r_4) = \textit{blue}$, but then we get the *blue* solution $2 + (1 + r_3 + r_4) = 3 + r_3 + r_4$.

Case 4. $r_2 = 2$. Suppose $\chi(7) = \textit{red}$. Then $\chi(4) = \textit{blue}$ (to avoid the *red* solution $1 + 2 + 4 = 7$) and $\chi(10) = \textit{blue}$ (to avoid the *red* solution $1 + 2 + 7 = 10$). This implies $\chi(6) = \textit{red}$ and $\chi(14) = \textit{red}$ to avoid the *blue* solutions $4 + 6 = 10$ and $4 + 10 = 14$, respectively. But then we get the *red* solution $1 + 6 + 7 = 14$. Therefore, $\chi(7) = \textit{blue}$.

Suppose $\chi(3) = \textit{blue}$. Then $\chi(4) = \textit{red}$ and $\chi(10) = \textit{red}$ to avoid the *blue* solutions $3 + 4 = 7$ and $3 + 7 = 10$, respectively. This implies $\chi(13) = \textit{blue}$ and $\chi(16) = \textit{blue}$ to avoid the *red* solutions $1 + 2 + 10 = 13$ and $2 + 4 + 10 = 16$, respectively. Therefore, $\chi(3) = \textit{red}$, which leads to a contradiction after a chain of implications:

- $\chi(6) = \textit{blue}$ (to avoid the *red* solution $1 + 2 + 3 = 6$),
- $\chi(13) = \textit{red}$ (to avoid the *blue* solution $6 + 7 = 13$),
- $\chi(9) = \textit{blue}$ (to avoid the *red* solution $1 + 3 + 9 = 13$),
- $\chi(16) = \textit{red}$ (to avoid the *blue* solution $7 + 9 = 16$),
- and hence the *red* solution $1 + 2 + 13 = 16$. □

4.1. Computer Assisted Proof for $S(3, 5)$

Let us write a coloring of $[1, n]$ as a bit-string of length n where the i -th bit is zero if $\chi(i) = \textit{blue}$, and one if $\chi(i) = \textit{red}$.

4.1.1. $S(3,5)=23$

By Lemma 1, the lower bound is $S(3, 5) > 22$. We consider all of the ten colorings of $[1, 22]$ (obtained by computer search) without a *blue* solution to L_3 and a *red* solution to L_5 .

1. For each of the following four colorings

0010110111111111111110,
 0010110111111011111110,
 0010110111111011011110, and
 0010110111101111011110,

if $\chi(23) = \textit{blue}$, then we have a *blue* solution $1 + 22 = 23$ to L_3 ; and
 if $\chi(23) = \textit{red}$, then we have a *red* solution $3 + 5 + 6 + 9 = 23$ to L_5 .

2. For each of the following four colorings

0010111011111111111101,
 0010111011111110111101,
 0010111011111101111101, and
 0010111011111011111101,

if $\chi(23) = \textit{blue}$, then we have a *blue* solution $2 + 21 = 23$ to L_3 ; and
 if $\chi(23) = \textit{red}$, then we have a *red* solution $3 + 5 + 6 + 9 = 23$ to L_5 .

3. For each of the following two colorings

010101010111111101010, and

01010101011111111010,

if $\chi(23) = \textit{blue}$, then we have a *blue* solution $1 + 22 = 23$ to L_3 ; and

if $\chi(23) = \textit{red}$, then we have a *red* solution $2 + 4 + 6 + 11 = 23$ to L_5 .

Therefore, $S(3, 5) = 23$.

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